

COHERENT SIMULATION AND TESTING FOR COMPOSITE BLADE REPAIR

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SUMMARY: The first phase of repair methodology under development is presented to illustrate the salient features on designing, testing and modeling the response of relevant coupons. The present emphasis is on developing appropriate test specimens to evaluate computationally and experimentally the effects of static and cyclic loads on sandwich panels.

KEYWORDS: helicopter blades, sandwich panels, glass/epoxy composite, FEA models

INTRODUCTION

The essentials of excellence in composite component design demand a priori assessment of repair methodology. As the design is enhanced with this knowledge base, the long term maintenance issues become less costly as well as leading to robust performance. The first phase addresses the design of the test coupons representative of overlap and scarf patch repairs and their analysis under static loading. The second phase evaluates the test matrix and the static tests conducted to evaluate the results of the computational effort.

A global blade model is used to identify potential repair sites for a typical flight condition. Identifying this region enables one to generate a local model with the appropriate boundary conditions so that different patch analyses can be carried on as well as recommending specimen configurations for testing. Cross-sectional models are generated from the local model for overlap and scarf patch simulation with finite elements. A failure subroutine, based on the ultimate stress allowable is incorporated into the analysis to detect the initiation and progression of failure. The shear stress distribution in the adhesive layer for the scarf patch model indicated that the stress is much higher in the interior away from the free surface. On the contrary, for the overlap configuration, the shear stress distribution reaches its maximum at the free edges.

In order to assess the structural response experimentally and computationally, composite sandwich test panels with scarf and overlap patches were designed and tested under static and fatigue loads. Two different panel sizes were used, 30.5 cm square (12 in) square for uniaxial tension test and 30.5 by 61 cm (12 by 24 in) rectangular panels for four point flexure test. Corresponding finite element simulations were developed to study the mechanical response.

EXPERIMENTS

The damaged area of the composite skin that is being repaired is circular with a 2.54 cm (1 in) diameter. Both patches, overlap and scarf, are 7.62 cm (3 in) in diameter, leaving 2.54 cm (1 in) between the edge of the damaged area and the end of the patch. The sandwich panels used have 2.54 cm (1 in) honeycomb cores with two 0.2286 mm (0.009 in) lamina on each side. The lamina are in a $\pm 45^\circ$ stacking sequence.

Square Panel

The square panels were tested under static and fatigue loads. The last 2.54 cm (1 in) of honeycomb core on each side of the panel is replaced by an aluminum tab in order to allow the load to be applied to the panel. A peak tensile load of 46.7 kN (10,500 lb) was applied. In tension-tension fatigue, maximum loads of 20.9 kN to 44.5 kN (4,700 to 10,000 lb) and a minimum load of 2.22 kN (500 lb) was applied to the panel.

A total of eight strain gauges were placed on the 30.5 cm (12 in) square panel when tested under static load. They measured axial and transverse as well as shear strain on various positions on the panel. Strain Gauges 1&3 were located between the aluminum tab and the patch and in the center of the patch, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Configuration of Tension Test on Square Panel

These gauges measured strain in the direction of loading. Cracks consistently initiated from the corners adjacent to the aluminum tabs, before or immediately after they did in the skin surrounding the patch. Cracks grew on a 45° diagonal along the fibers adjacent to the patch. Few or no cracks were seen in the patch and the patch remained in tact during testing. Nonlinearities in the load Vs displacement curve first appear between 17.8 kN & 26.7 kN (4,000 & 6,000 lb) of tensile load. In the tension-tension fatigue tests with an $R=5.5$, visible

cracks in the unpatched panel were observed at the corners around 320,000 cycles. Under equivalent conditions the panel with an overlap patch exhibited initial cracks at 1,500,000 cycles from the patch and at 1,800,000 cycles from the corner. It is noted that as R was increased, earlier crack initiation was routinely observed. The edge effects at the tabs inhibit our ability to experimentally evaluate the response between repaired and original panels.

Rectangular Panel

In order to eliminate stress concentration due to fixture and grips, the 30.5 by 61 cm (12 by 24 in) panels were designed for flex loading. During the testing, the load for core crushing under the loading bars was identified and relevant adjustments were made to the location of support and load bars. The rectangular panel is being tested under four point bending conditions as illustrated in Fig. 2. The distance between the supports was 45.72 cm (18 in). The distance between the loading lines was either 15.24 or 22.86 cm (6 or 9 in).

Fig. 2 Side view of Rectangular Bending Tests

COMPUTATIONAL MODELS

A quarter model of the panel is modeled with symmetry boundary conditions. with S8R composite shell elements from the ABAQUS element library. These elements have five degrees of freedom u_x , u_y , u_z , Θ_x & Θ_y at each node. The through the thickness material details were incorporated to address the presence of the patch, adhesive, skin and honeycomb as shown in Fig. 2. The skin and honeycomb were treated as orthotropic where as the adhesive layer was assumed to be an isotropic material. A hypothetical material with minimal

stiffness is used in the unpatched region of the panel to align every integration point (3 per layer) through the thickness of each element

Square Panel: Uniaxial Tension Load

Strains from the ABAQUS models are compared to the test data in Figs. 3 & 4. The skin was modeled with homogenized properties. In the subsequent simulations, the skin was taken as two discrete layers.

Fig. 3 Experimental & FEA Axial Strains

Fig. 4 Experimental & FEA Axial Strains

With a linear analysis simulating 17.8 kN (4,000 lb) of loading and discrete properties for the ± 45 degree layers, peak strains in the panel were at the corner adjacent to the aluminum tab. The ratio of strain to strain allowable in the patch and in the skin surrounding the patch is significantly less than at the corner. Since the strain allowable in the direction transverse to the fiber is less than parallel to the fiber, failure initiation is expected as matrix cracking and splitting. The deformed shape (magnified sixty six times) and the undeformed shape of the panel are presented in Fig. 5 at a tensile load of 17.8 kN (4,000 lb). At this loading conditions there is a reduction in crosshead displacement, D , of 3.4% between the patch with a panel and the unpatched panel. This represents a minimal increase in stiffness due to the addition of an overlap patch over the unpatched panel. Next, the panel was modeled incorporating a user

material subroutine UMAT to model the weakening of the skin after strain allowables have been reached. In this model a total simulated load of 44.5 kN (10,000 lb) is applied in ten increments. The subroutine checks maximum strain theory at each increment and every integration point. Maximum strains in the direction transverse to the fibers in the +45° layer of the modeled

1

Fig. 5 Deformed & Undeformed Shape of Square Panel

The subroutine checks maximum strain theory at each increment and every integration point. Maximum strains in the direction transverse to the fibers in the +45° layer of the modeled region are seen at the corner node where the aluminum tab is adjacent to the honeycomb core. This is illustrated in Fig. 6, where each point represents an increment and 4.45 kN (1,000 lb) of additional loading to the panel. In the linear range, stresses where the aluminum tab replaces the honeycomb core are roughly twice those around the patch. Once strain allowables are reached at the corner and the material is weakened, higher stress is seen in the skin around the patch. This indicates that edge effects from the tabs are greatly affecting the stress & strain concentrations in the skin surrounding the patch.

Fig. 6 Stress Versus Strain at Corner Node in Square Model

Rectangular Panel: Flexure Load

Four point flex test geometry was modeled with two different spacings between load and support bars. In both configurations, the patch is located on the tension side of the panel, and the distance between supports is 45.7 cm (18 in). In the first configuration the distance between loading bars is 15.24 cm (6 in), and in the second the distance is 22.9 cm (9 in). On fourth of the panel was modeled with 272 S8R elements from the ABAQUS library. Similar to the square panel case, symmetry boundary conditions were placed along the edges to reduce the overall amount of computation.

The peak strain region in the second configuration first occurs in the skin immediately surrounding the patch. The actual deformed shape is shown in Fig. 7 that corresponds to a total of 6.23 kN (1400 lb).

Fig. 7 Actual Displacement of Quarter Point Bending Model

Peak strain ratios, predicted strain divided by strain allowable, indicate that the region of skin immediately surrounding the patch is more likely to fail than the patch itself at a load of 10.2 kN (2,300 lb). Experiments revealed that skin crimping occurred at 11.6 kN (2,600 lb).

CONCLUSIONS

Sandwich panels were designed to establish criteria to assess the effectiveness of relevant blade repairs under static and dynamic load conditions. The integrated computational and experimental approach enabled the successive design improvements to the test panels. The analytical predictions for static tensile and flex load conditions are in excellent agreement with the tests.

The fatigue flexure testing with and without reversed loading is underway and computational assessment for fatigue response is being developed based on energy formulation

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The financial support and the technical interaction provided by Bell Helicopter Textron, Inc. is graciously acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. Oztelcan C, "Design and Analysis of Test Coupons for Composite Blade Repairs", Master's Thesis, Texas A&M University, May 1996
2. Oztelcan C., Ochoa, O.O., Martin, J. and Sem, K., " Design and Analysis of Test Coupons for Composite Blade Repair", *Journal of Composite Structures*, accepted for publication, January 1996.